

Temporomandibular Joint Disorders: A Review Article

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Submitted 23 February 2026
Accepted 27 February 2026
Published 12 June 2026

Access this article online
Website : www.updent.in
DOI

Abstract

Temporomandibular disorders (TMDs) comprise a group of musculoskeletal conditions involving the temporomandibular joint, masticatory muscles, and associated structures. They commonly present with orofacial pain, joint sounds, and restricted mandibular movement. The etiology is multifactorial, involving mechanical, psychological, and behavioral factors. Diagnosis is based on detailed history, clinical examination, and appropriate imaging to exclude other pathologies. Most cases are self-limiting and respond well to conservative management, including patient education, pharmacotherapy, physical therapy, and occlusal splints. A multidisciplinary approach is essential for effective long-term management and improved patient outcomes.

Keywords: Temporomandibular disorders; Temporomandibular joint; Orofacial pain; Myofascial pain dysfunction; Internal derangement; Bruxism; Occlusal splint therapy; TMJ osteoarthritis; RDC/TMD; Conservative management

Introduction

Temporomandibular joint (TMJ) disorder refers to a cluster of conditions characterized by pain in the TMJ or its surrounding tissues, functional limitations of the mandible, or clicking in the TMJ during motion.^{1,2} TMJ disorders are common and often self-limited in the adult population. In epidemiologic studies, up to 75 percent of adults show at least one sign of joint dysfunction on examination and as many as one third have at least one symptom.^{2,3}

Anatomy of the temporomandibular joint

What are TMDs?

Some of the signs and symptoms suggestive of TMDs were identified back in

the 1930s by Costen, who incorrectly attributed them to changes in occlusion (bite of the teeth). Over the next 80 years the terminology has changed and been revised several times^{4,5,6,7} until the collective term temporomandibular disorders has been accepted. The most widely accepted definition is “a group of musculoskeletal conditions that involve the temporomandibular joints (TMJs), the masticatory muscles and all associated tissues.”^{8,9,10} A new expanded taxonomy is now available defining the various subtypes of disorder or disease incorporated in this group.^{11,12}

Etiology

The TMJ is a synovial joint that contains an articular disk, which allows for hinge and sliding movements. This complex combination of movements allows for painless and efficient chewing, swallowing, and speaking.¹³ The articulating surfaces of the TMJ are covered by a fibrous connective tissue; this avascular and non innervated structure has a greater capacity to resist degener-

How to Cite This Article : Yadav et al. -

ative change and regenerate itself than the hyaline cartilage of other synovial joints.¹³ The synovial joint capsule and surrounding musculature are innervated, however, and are thought to be the primary source of pain in TMJ disorders. The etiology of TMJ disorders remains unclear, but it is likely multifactorial. Capsule inflammation or damage and muscle pain or spasm may be caused by abnormal occlusion, parafunctional habits (e.g., bruxism [teeth grinding], teeth clenching, lip biting), stress, anxiety, or abnormalities of the intra-articular disk. In recent years, many of the theories about the development of TMJ disorders have been questioned. Abnormal dental occlusion appears to be equally common in persons with and without TMJ symptoms,^{1,14} and occlusal correction does not reliably improve the symptoms or signs of TMJ disorders.^{2,15} Parafunctional habits have been thought to cause TMJ microtrauma or masticatory muscle hyperactivity⁹; however, these habits are also common in asymptomatic patients. Although parafunctional habits may play a role in initiating or perpetuating symptoms in some patients, the cause-and-effect relationship remains uncertain.¹⁶ There is some evidence to suggest that anxiety, stress, and other emotional disturbances may exacerbate TMJ disorders, especially in patients who experience chronic pain.¹⁶ As many as 75 percent of patients with TMJ disorders have a significant psychological abnormality.¹⁸ Recognition and treatment of concomitant mental illness is important in the overall approach to management of chronic pain, including pain caused by TMJ disorders.

Diagnosis

Clinical Examination

Common symptoms of TMJ disorders include jaw pain, limited or painful jaw movement, headache, neck pain or stiffness, clicking or grating within the joint, and, occasionally, an inability to open the mouth painlessly.^{2,17} Most adults with these symptoms do not seek medical or dental treatment. It is not clear which symptoms are more common in which TMJ disorders; however, it is generally assumed that joint clicking or grating signifies intra-articular derangement whereas headache, neck pain, or painful jaw movement suggests a muscular problem. Examination of the TMJ and masticatory muscles should include careful palpation of all structures. Myospasm and myofascial trigger points may be determined by palpation of the masseter or sternocleidomastoid muscles,¹⁸ which can be performed by placing a finger over the TMJ or into the ear canal while the patient opens and closes the mouth. A clicking or popping sensation that occurs during mouth opening may indicate displacement of the intra-articular disk during mandibular movement.¹⁹ Pain or swelling localized to the TMJ can indicate intra-articular inflammation. Clicking is a common symptom and is part of the diagnostic criteria for TMJ disorders; however, joint sounds do not necessarily correlate with pain severity or functional limitation. Therefore, the absence of clicking sounds is not a reliable symptom to use in determining whether the patient has responded to treatment.¹⁶ Absence of pain, improved function, and normal

quality of life are more appropriate markers of treatment success.

Classification

Research has been hindered by the lack of clear diagnostic criteria for TMJ disorders; however, two groups have developed diagnostic classification systems. The American Academy of Orofacial Pain published a diagnostic classification system in 1995.⁸ Also, the Research Diagnostic Criteria for Temporomandibular Disorders (RDC/TMD) tool was created and validated by the International Consortium for RDC/TMD-based Research.¹³ These two classification systems are not identical, but are substantially similar.¹⁴ An abbreviated version of the diagnostic classification system developed by the American Academy of Orofacial Pain is shown in Table 1.⁸ TMJ disorders are separated into two main categories based on the anatomic origin of the problem: articular disorders and masticatory muscle disorders. Articular disorders include the articular surface, intra-articular disk, or articulating bones.^{8,11} Masticatory muscle disorders are problems within the muscles surrounding the TMJ. Accurate recognition of the origin of pain, either intra-articular or muscular, may help the physician recommend an initial therapy; however, it is not clear which non invasive therapies work best.⁸

Articular disorders of the TMJ

Ankylosis

Congenital or developmental disorders

Aplasia, hyperplasia, or hypoplasia of the cranial bones or mandible

Neoplasia of the TMJ or associated structures

Disk derangement disorders

Articular disk displacement with or without reduction

Fracture of the condylar process

Inflammatory disorders

Synovitis, capsulitis, polyarthritides including the TMJ

Osteoarthritis

TMJ dislocation

Masticatory muscle disorders

Local myalgia (unclassified)

Myofascial pain

Myofibrotic contracture

Myositis

Myospasm

Neoplasia

Table 1. Diagnostic classification of TMJ Disorders¹⁶

Clinical Features

There are three cardinal features of temporomandibular disorders orofacial pain, joint noise, and restricted jaw function. Pain is the most common presenting complaint and is by far the most difficult problem to evaluate.¹⁹⁻²¹ Joint noise, however, is quite common in asymptomatic people in the general population, and is of little clinical importance in the absence of pain.^{21, 22} Restricted jaw function encompasses a limited range of mandibular movements in all directions. Like

pain, restricted jaw function causes considerable anxiety for the patient, who faces difficulties in everyday activities such as eating and speaking. Patients describe either a generalised tight feeling, which is probably a muscular disorder, or the sensation that the jaw suddenly “catches” or “gets stuck,” which is usually related to internal derangement.²¹ Headaches, earaches, tinnitus, and neck and shoulder pains are just a few of a number of non-specific symptoms that are often reported by patients with temporomandibular disorders²². However since these symptoms are not considered to be specific for temporomandibular disorders, other possible causes should be sought and ruled out.²³

Clinical Evaluation

History

The main complaint may include orofacial pain, joint noises, restricted mouth opening, or a combination of these, in addition to other less specific problems such as headache and tinnitus. Pain should be evaluated carefully in terms of its onset, nature, intensity, site, duration, aggravating and relieving factors, and, especially, how it relates to the other features such as joint noise and restricted mandibular movements. More specifically, pain that is centred immediately in front of the tragus of the ear and projects to the ear, temple, cheek, and along the mandible is highly diagnostic for temporomandibular disorder. The pain may be accompanied by a click or grating sound in the preauricular region during mandibular functions such as chewing or yawning. A history of limited mouth opening, which may be intermittent or progressive, is also a key feature of temporomandibular disorders. Chronic head, neck, and back pain; irritable bowel syndrome; and idiopathic pruritus are sometimes found in patients with temporomandibular disorders and should be sought by the doctor to help establish the possibility of a psychogenic cause. The doctor should also ask the patient about underlying influences such as stress, anxiety, depression, or important life events so that he or she can get a clearer picture of any psychogenic basis to the disorder.^{21,23,24,25} In general, the longer the duration of the symptoms and the greater the number of treatments, and in particular “failed” treatments, the smaller the likelihood that the patient will respond well to further treatment²⁵

Clinical Examination

The patient should be evaluated for tenderness in those areas of the head and neck that are accessible to palpation. Palpation is accomplished by placing the finger tips in the preauricular region just in front of the tragus of the ear. The patient is then asked to open their mouth and the fingertip will fall into the depression left by the translating condyle²⁵. Examination of the masticatory musculature may also be accomplished by digital palpation. Areas of tenderness,

trigger points, and patterns of pain referral should be noted. Joint sounds and their location during opening, closing, and lateral excursions of the mandible may be either palpated or detected with a stethoscope placed over the preauricular area. Mandibular function may be evaluated by noting whether the line of vertical opening is straight and smooth or deviates with jerky movements. The range of painless maximal vertical opening (normal range 42-55 mm interincisal distance) should be recorded^{24,25}.

Investigations

Investigations are mainly required to eliminate the possibility of other abnormalities that may mimic temporomandibular disorder symptoms.^{26,27} Despite the limitations, plain radiographs of the temporomandibular joint such as high level orthopantomograms and transcranial projections are useful ways of visualising any gross pathological, degenerative, or traumatic changes in the bony component of the temporomandibular joint complex²⁶. In recent years, magnetic resonance imaging has been used increasingly to investigate temporomandibular disorders, in particular, internal derangements of the temporomandibular joint. Many other investigations such as computed tomography and arthroscopy have been advocated^{25,26}.

Diagnosis

Myofascial pain and dysfunction generally presents with diffuse pain that is cyclic and found in several sites in the head and neck, particularly the muscles of mastication. Pain is frequently worst in the morning, and the patient will often report sore teeth from clenching. There is often a history of stress and difficulty in sleeping. The patient will present with diffuse muscle tenderness and a decreased range of mandibular movements with wear facets on the teeth. Internal joint derangement, however, presents with continuous pain that is localised to the temporomandibular joint and is exacerbated by jaw movement. Mechanical interferences in the joint, such as clicking and locking, will often result in restricted mandibular opening or deviation of mandibular movements during opening and closing. Crepitus or grating sounds emanating from the joint(s) during mandibular function is pathognomonic of temporomandibular joint osteoarthritis in the elderly. Where the condition is painful, it is referred to as osteoarthritis. Computed tomograms of the temporomandibular joint will often show degeneration and flattening of the condylar head. Most patients seem to cope well with osteoarthritis as it rarely leads to limited mandibular function. Where computed tomograms show similar condylar changes in younger patients, other arthritides, such as rheumatoid arthritis, should be considered and investigated further²⁷.

Condition	Symptoms	Signs
Dental pathology		
Tooth abscess	Pain with chewing over affected tooth	Visible tooth decay; fluctuance along gum line; pain with palpation over the tooth
Wisdom tooth eruption	Dull ache behind posterior molars	Tenderness to palpation over emerging tooth
Infection or inflammation		
Herpes zoster and postherpetic neuralgia	Prodrome of pain followed by vesicular rash	Vesicular rash in dermatomal distribution, not crossing midline
Mastoiditis	Fever; otalgia	Postauricular erythema and swelling; tenderness over mastoid process
Otitis externa	Pruritus, pain, and tenderness of the external ear	Erythema and edema of external auditory canal
Otitis media	Fever; malaise; otalgia	Tympanic membrane dull, bulging, erythematous; loss of landmarks on tympanic membrane
Parotitis	Fever; malaise; myalgia; pain over parotid gland	Tenderness and induration over parotid gland
Sialadenitis	Pain and swelling of involved salivary gland	Tenderness, induration, and/or erythema of salivary gland; usually unilateral
Trigeminal neuralgia	Paroxysmal, unilateral lancinating pains in trigeminal nerve distribution	Examination generally normal

Table 2. Differential Diagnosis of orofacial Pain

Treatment Planning

The clinical course of temporomandibular disorders does not reflect a progressive disease, but rather a complex disorder moulded by many interacting factors that serve to maintain the disease.^{18,12,24-26} The main goals of treatment for temporomandibular disorders are to reduce or eliminate pain or joint noises, or both, and to restore normal mandibular function. This is best achieved when other contributing factors such as stress, depression, and oral parafunctional habits (such as bruxism) are addressed and incorporated into the overall treatment strategy.²⁷

Self-Care : There is little evidence to suggest that any TMJ disorder treatment modality is superior to any other, although it is generally accepted that self-care and behavioral interventions should be encouraged for all patients, regard less of which therapies are considered.¹⁶ Providing a few simple exercises, behavioral instructions, and reassurance are important steps when treating the average patient with new or intermittent symptoms^{16,28}.

Table 3. Noninvasive Therapies for TMJ Disorders

Alternative therapies	Physical therapy modalities	
Acupressure	Biofeedback	
Acupuncture	Iontophoresis	
Hypnosis	Phonophoresis	
Massage	Superficial or deep heat	
Dental procedures		
Temporary occlusal therapy	Therapeutic exercise	
	Lateral jaw movement	
	Protrusive jaw movement	
Medical interventions		
Intra-articular corticosteroid or anesthetic injection	Resisted closing	
Myofascial trigger-point injection	Resisted opening	
Pharmacologic treatment	Tongue-up exercise	
Acetaminophen	Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation	
Anxiolytics	Psychological interventions	
Benzodiazepines	Cognitive behavior therapy	
Muscle relaxants	Relaxation techniques	
Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs	Stress management	
Tricyclic antidepressants		

TMJ = temporomandibular joint.

Non Invasive Therapy : Many noninvasive therapies are commonly used for the treatment of TMJ disorders. The disciplines of medicine, dentistry, physical therapy, and psychology can all provide effective treatment. Because most patients with TMJ disorders improve with or without treatment, these conservative therapies should be encouraged before invasive treatments are considered.^{16,28}

Pharmacologic Intervention : Pharmacologic interventions similar to those for other musculoskeletal disorders are a treatment option. Acetaminophen and non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs can help with acute and chronic pain. For muscle spasm and chronic bruxism, muscle relaxants or benzodiazepines may be necessary if conservative relaxation techniques fail. Tricyclic anti-depressants may help with pain, including pain from nighttime bruxism.^{16,28} Antidepressants that are used in the treatment of chronic pain syndromes might also be beneficial in the treatment of chronic TMJ disorders. However, care should be used when prescribing selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors because there have been rare case reports of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor-induced bruxism.³⁰

Intra-Articular Injections : Intra-articular injections of the TMJ with local anesthetics or corticosteroids can be used for the treatment of inflammation within the TMJ capsule.⁸ Intra-articular injection should only be used for severe acute exacerbations or after conservative therapies have been unsuccessful.¹⁶ Repeated intra-articular corticosteroid injections are not recommended. A recent systematic review found insufficient evidence to encourage the use of intra-articular hyaluronate for the treatment of TMJ pathology. Local anesthetics and botulinum toxin (Botox) can also be used in myofascial trigger-point injections for the treatment of chronic bruxism.^{16,29}

Dental Occlusion Therapy : Dental occlusal splinting and permanent occlusal adjustment have been the mainstays of TMJ disorder treatment for years, although there is no clear evidence that malocclusion of the upper and lower teeth causes TMJ pain.¹⁶ Two main types of splinting are available: occluding and non occluding. Occluding splints, also called stabilization splints, are specially fabricated to improve the alignment of the upper and lower teeth.²⁰⁻²² Non occluding splints, also called simple splints, primarily open the jaw, release muscle tension, and prevent teeth clenching. Occluding splints need to be fabricated and adjusted by a trained dentist and may cost several hundred dollars in overall treatment costs.¹² Non occluding splints are typically made of a soft vinyl and are easier and cheaper to fabricate. Inexpensive versions can usually be purchased at local pharmacies. Permanent occlusal adjustment can be obtained through orthodontics or by grinding down the superficial tooth enamel to improve occlusion.¹⁶ The Cochrane Collaboration recently reviewed permanent occlusal adjustment and occluding splint therapy for treatment of TMJ disorders.^{2,15} There was insufficient evidence to show benefit or harm with either treatment.^{2,15} Also, several trials comparing occluding and non occluding splint

therapy have shown no significant differences in long-term treatment outcomes. Occlusal adjustment, either permanent or temporary, can still be an appropriate treatment for dental pathology, but its role in the primary treatment of TMJ disorders is uncertain.¹⁶

Manual Reduction In Acute Disk Displacement

Acute anterior displacement of the intra articular disk is a rare condition that causes the jaw to lock in the open position. This can lead to painful inflammation in the articular capsule and can inhibit swallowing and eating. Most patients with acute locking of the jaw have a history of episodic locking, a noticeable click with chewing, or a habit of teeth clenching.³¹ Disk displacement should be reduced as soon as possible. If the patient is unable to reduce the displacement by laterally moving the mandible and opening the mouth wide, manual reduction should be attempted. Manual reduction of the disk can usually be achieved by inserting the thumb into the patient's mouth, grasping under the chin, and simultaneously pushing down on the posterior teeth and pulling up on the chin. The mandibular condyle will be distracted downward, allowing the disk to move posteriorly into place.³¹ The patient's head should be stabilized, either by the examiner's opposite hand or a headrest or wall. A local anesthetic or intravenous benzodiazepine may be used to decrease pain and relax severe spasm before manual reduction.

Conclusion

Temporomandibular disorders are multifactorial conditions affecting the temporomandibular joint and associated musculature, commonly presenting with pain, joint sounds, and restricted mandibular movement. Accurate diagnosis based on thorough clinical evaluation and appropriate investigations is essential for effective management. Most cases respond well to conservative and non-invasive therapies, including patient education, behavioral modification, pharmacologic support, and occlusal appliances. Early recognition and a multidisciplinary approach addressing both physical and psychological factors are crucial in achieving pain relief, restoring function, and improving overall quality of life in patients with temporomandibular disorders.

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